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Title:

The contribution of artificial intelligence to the assessment of medical interventions for depression in adults with epilepsy

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Introduction : Large language models (LLMs), which serve as the foundation for contemporary chatbots, are capable of mimicking human language and swiftly producing responses that seem comprehensive and logical. However, these characteristics may conceal the risk of chatbots spreading incorrect information. As patients increasingly turn to the internet for self-education, it is likely that some will seek medical advice from LLM-powered chatbots. This reliance could result in the generation and spread of misleading information. Moreover, since these models lack critical thinking and medical expertise, their responses are not always reliable, particularly in the context of complex medical conditions. Consequently, while LLMs can provide general information, they should not be used as substitutes for professional medical guidance.

Objectives : Our objective was to evaluate the alignment of ChatGPT's recommendations for the medical treatment of depression in adults with epilepsy with established ILAE guidelines.[1] [2] Specifically, we aimed to assess whether the suggestions provided by ChatGPT adhered to the most recent standards outlined by the International League Against Epilepsy (ILAE) for managing comorbid depression in patients with epilepsy. Given the increasing use of AI-based tools in healthcare, it is crucial to understand how well these models can align with expert-recommended treatment protocols. This evaluation also sought to identify potential discrepancies or gaps in ChatGPT's responses that might affect its clinical utility in providing evidence-based recommendations for depression treatment in this patient population.

Methods : We created a zero-shot prompt template for inquiring about treatment recommendations. This template enabled the generation of 15 questions, aligned with the 2022 ILAE guidelines. Each question underwent three iterations. Our evaluation compared responses obtained with and without the use of prompt engineering techniques, which involve specifying roles, tasks, and instructions. These prompts were randomly fed into the ChatGPT4 model through the OpenAI interface. The responses were assessed by six researchers with expertise in the field. A five-point scale was employed (ranging from 1 for poor to 5 for excellent), and the evaluation covered seven criteria for each response: alignment with ILAE recommendations, accuracy, occurrence of "hallucinations," relevance, comprehensiveness, empathy, and overall quality score. Each researcher conducted their assessment independently, without access to the evaluations of their peers.

Results : ChatGPT consistently utilized a systematic approach in addressing queries, frequently recommending that users seek personalized advice tailored to their specific health needs and circumstances. However, when faced with prompts that do not have clear directives, ChatGPT's responses often varied from partially to wholly misaligned with established guidelines. In contrast, when queries were formulated using precise prompt engineering methods, ChatGPT's responses generally adhered to the guidelines, though they were often deemed satisfactory but insufficient. [3]

Conclusions : The treatment of depression in adults with epilepsy requires a highly personalized approach. Although ChatGPT delivers thorough and articulate responses, it cannot replace the tailored care provided by medical experts.

References

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Topics:

Artificial Intelligence and computational models

Digital Health

Neurological disorders

Appendix

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